

PAPER A: RESEARCH ARTICLE

Digester Fabrication for Biogas Production from Fruit Wastes and Kinetic Models

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Abstract

Biogas production requires a digester with built-in stirring system to keep the content homogeneous as well as a gas collection chamber. In this case, a slight modification of an existing container to suit the description above was made to produce biogas separately from banana, orange, pineapple, watermelon peels, sugarcane bagasse and the whole fruit waste (FW) blend over a period of 30 days. Gas yield obtained, as used in the estimation of biogas potential of the respective FW, lag phase duration and rate of gas generation from modified Gompertz, Logistic and First-Order models, shows that the modified Gompertz, best fits the empirical biogas measurement. Future work should look at the effect of pretreating the feedstock and the addition of additives to maximize gas production.

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Keywords: Biogas yield, Modified Gompertz, Logistic, Bioreactor, First-Order, Biogas model

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1.0. | Introduction

Digesters or bioreactors as synonymously termed in the literature are air-tight containers meant for degrading organic waste matters in the presence of microbes to generate biogas

and digestate/biofertilizer. Conventional types such as fixed-dome and balloon or tubular bioreactor are known for large scale biogas production (Abubakar, Silas, et al., 2022; Osueke et al., 2018). Small scale or laboratory-scale type are available

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in different shapes, design and configurations depending on specification of the users (Jyothilakshmi & Prakash, 2016). Fortunately, both conventional and fabricated digester types can be used to decompose any kind of feedstock (Obileke et al., 2020; Onucha et al., 2019). Normally, feedstock charged into biodigesters can be categorized into agricultural, municipal and industrial wastes.

Fruit wastes (FW) can be placed under agricultural and municipal waste (Jaysingpure & Khobragade, 2022; Majeed & Malik, 2018). However, municipal wastes are the chief source of FW since most agricultural harvest are transported to cities where they are consumed. In that case, FW are found as part of household waste, kitchen waste, street litter, market place and at dumpsites. The organic matter is rich in macro- and micro-nutrient needed by microorganisms to decompose it to biogas. Other conditions like temperature, moisture content, toxic presence, pH, protein, carbohydrate, lipids, carbon-to-nitrogen (C/N) ratio and ash content affects the yield and survival of microbes inside the digester (Bhajani, 2022). Duration of digestion are sometimes fixed or made to be dependent on nutrient availability of the substrate. As such, in some instances, biogas production is discontinued when no more noticeable biogas is generated with time or when the microbial population has declined. Typical example are the production of biogas from FW, previously experimented by Narayani & Ponnaiah (2012), Sagagi et al. (2009), Chakravarty & Mandavgane (2021), Chinwendu et al. (2019), dos Santos et al. (2020) and Rahmat et al. (2019).

Yield of biogas has been modelled using several kinetic models, encapsulating microbial growth, biogas potential, cumulative biogas yield, lag phase and pretreatment. However, the most widely used category of all models already developed previously is the biogas kinetic models. Example of such models are the modified Gompertz, Logistic, First-Order, Transference, Transfert, Cone and Fritzburg model to mention a few (Abubakar, et al., 2022; Moharir et al., 2020; Oyaro et al., 2020). They are used to predict bioreactor efficiency, potentials of a particular feedstock for biogas production and the ability of the experimental results to explain the kinetic parameters estimated.

So, the objectives of the work are to modify an existing container to suit the basic requirement of a digester; characterize FW including banana, orange, pineapple, watermelon peels, sugarcane bagasse and their blend;

produce biogas separately from each of the six wastes; and use existing kinetic model to determine the performance of the process.

2.0. | Materials and Methods

2.1.1. | Fruit Waste Collection, Drying and Grinding

10 kg each of banana peels, orange peels, pineapple peels, watermelon peels and sugarcane bagasse are collected. The sixth was a blend of 2kg each of banana, orange, pineapple, watermelon and sugarcane bagasse to make a total of 10 kg FW blend.

The waste was separately kept in six large container-like bioreactors and labelled as shown in [Table 1](#).

Table 1: Fruit Waste Collection

Label	Fruit Peel	Weight (kg)
A	Banana	10
B	Orange	10
C	Pineapple	10
D	Watermelon	10
E	Sugarcane bagasse	10
F	Blend	10

Sufficient water was poured in each of the containers to wash away soil contaminants from the FW. This was done to ensure a pure sample of the waste and a clean nutrient for bacteria to feed on during digestion.

Sample A to F are allowed to partially sun-dry under the prevailing weather condition. It was then cut to smaller sizes to reduce difficult injecting them into the digester.

2.1.2. | Laboratory Analysis

Sample A, B, C, D, E and F were analyzed for metallic nutrient content using EDXRF analyzer. Total solid or dry matter percentage in the samples as well as the volatile solid, ash content, moisture content of the samples were determined using electric furnace and laboratory drying oven. The nitrogen content was determined using Kjeldahl method and the protein content was calculated. Other nutrient content like carbohydrate and lipids as well as the carbon content was experimented. The C/N ratio in each of the sample was then calculated. Using a pH and temperature meters, the initial pH and temperature of samples A-F was measured and recorded.

2.1.3. | *Fabrication of Digesters (Pilot-Scale)*

A digester is a container-like bioreactor that is made of either plastic, polyethylene or metal with feedstock inlet, digestate outlet, stirrer and a gas outlet to keep the environment of the substrate within it at a desired condition for bacteria to decompose them and generate biogas.

A cylindrical container of 50 cm high and made of steel iron is re-shaped to include a handle, gas outlet metallic tube, a stirrer, feedstock inlet and by-product outlet. The top of the cylinder is cut open using oxyacetylene flame, sufficiently enough to insert a stirrer. An iron rod was welded to produce a stirrer with two shaft stirring end and an L-shape handle. The stirrer was inserted into the container and welded, so that only the stirring shaft is inside while the handle is outside. A nut is used to fasten the stirrer to the top of the cylindrical digester to allow free rotation despite being oxygen tight. A handle was welded to the digester top surface to enable users carry the digester easily. A very narrow opening-like pipe was welded to the digester top to connect a ½ -inch pipe to a car tube. This would serve as a passage of gas out of the digester to the tube.

2.1.4. | *Feedstock Digestion/Digestion Period*

Six laboratory scale plastic digesters were labelled A, B, C, D, E and F according to FW type. The digesters are ensured clean and dry before pouring the dried sample to their respective digesters. Water was added to all the samples inside the container so that the water to sample ratio is 1:1. The mixture was mixed thoroughly using a stirrer or by shaking the plastic digester vigorously. Cow dung, 300g each was added to the digesters to serve as inoculum. The cow dung contains bacteria and other microorganism. A small balloon or tube was connected to the respective digesters using a tube to trap the generated gas. A small non-return was fix to the pipe to control gas flow.

The weight of the six tubes or balloons were recorded empty. The digesters inlet and outlet were kept tightly closed not allowing oxygen to contaminate the environment of the microorganisms. Every 24 hours the valve was partially open to allow the newly generated gas inside the digester to flow to the balloon via the pipe connected. The new weight of the balloon was recorded. Immediately it is done, the value was tightly closed. This step was repeated daily for 30 days. Gas

generated is equivalent to weight recorded on a certain day minus weight of balloon recorded the previous day. The raw gas generated needs to be purified before use.

2.1.5. | *Biogas Analysis*

The gas trapped in the tube or balloon is the biogas generated and is a mixture of CH₄, CO₂, O₂, H₂S, moisture, NH₃ and N₂. The cumulative value of the weight recorded for a period of 30 days was determined. This was used to analyze the production by determining the lag phase, the biogas potential of the respective samples A-F and the maximum biogas production rate using biogas kinetic model.

The models are respectively the modified Gompertz model, the Logistic model and the First-Order models, according to Eqn. 1, 2 and 3 (Abubakar, et al., 2022; Moharir et al., 2020);

$$CBY = BP \exp^{-\exp\left[\frac{k_e}{BP}(LP-t)+1\right]} \quad (1)$$

$$CBY = \frac{BP}{1 + \exp\left[\frac{4k(LP-t)}{BP} + 2\right]} \quad (2)$$

$$CBY = BP(1 - \exp(-kt)) \quad (3)$$

where, CBY = cumulative biogas yield (kg), BP = biogas potential (kg), k = biogas production rate (kg), LP = lag phase (day) and t = retention time (or RT) (day). Using the Excel Solver regression tool, the model parameters were estimated by fitting them to the model line of plot of the experimented CBY with time. Several plots were made to compare deviation from the empirical result and comments on the model's ability to produce fitted lines of the predicted CBY.

3.0. | **Results and Discussion**

3.1.1. | *Digester Fabrication*

Batch scale bioreactor as used previously by Deepanraj et al. (2015) to study the kinetics of biogas production is the model adopted in this work. The digester fabricated is as shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Modified Cylindrical Container Used as Bioreactor

Shape is not normally a case when constructing or designing digesters for biogas production. However, size is of great importance, as it defines whether the production is large scale or small scale. Use of metallic cylinder will prevent the digester from breaking compared to a plastic-type digester and last longer. Painting the digester black would enable adequate regulation of heat within the digester for the microorganism's survival. As they survive at four different temperature regimes, including mesophilic, thermophilic, psychrophilic, and hyper-thermophilic temperature regimes.

The design in Fig. 1 is similar to most designs available out there. A digester must have an inlet through which the organic waste (say FW) can be fed, slurry/digestate outlet, gas outlet and a stirrer in some situations. The gas outlet is usually connected to a gas holder and the stirrer is used to keep the content uniform. In this case, temperature, pH, nutrient content and microbial distribution within the feed must be uniform for a harmonious process.

3.1.2. | Fruit Waste Characterization

The characterized fresh samples of the FW and the blend before feeding into the digestion is as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Physio-chemical Analysis of the Fruit Waste Sample

Analysis	A (%)	B (%)	C (%)	D (%)	E (%)	F (%)
Total Solid	89.9	90.4	57.2	60.66	92.12	78.06
Volatile Solid	12.42	20.12	9.95	15.56	10.18	13.65
Ash Content	2.5	5.49	4.41	3.93	6.55	4.58
Moisture Content	10.1	9.6	42.8	39.34	7.88	21.94
Nitrogen Content	1.22	2.63	1.79	2.14	1.34	1.82
Protein Content	7.63	16.42	11.19	13.35	8.39	11.40
Carbohydrate Content	85	55	64	71	86	72.2
Lipid Content	6.39	14.43	6.77	9.87	16.51	10.79
Carbon Content	42.37	33.22	24.43	38.12	40.10	35.65
C/N Ratio	34.73	12.63	13.65	17.81	29.93	21.75

Feedstock with adequate amount of nutrient content, C/N ratio and carbon content are essential for the growth and proliferation of microorganisms within a digester. Some of these compositions are in-line with data reported by Abubakar & Yunus (2021). Even though, as part initial preparation of the feedstock where the FW are cut into smaller parts, it would still require the addition of water as earlier explained. Microorganisms moves conveniently within the digester if content is slurrified and will facilitate easy mixing using the stirrer. However, values obtained in Table 2 cannot be a standard for each of the sample as they fall between agreeable range in the literature. Depletion of the nutrient content inside any of reactor A-F will signify completion of the anaerobic digestion process; likewise, the micro- and macro-element shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Metallic Compositions of the Selected Fruit Waste

Model	Parameters	Banana	Orange	Pineapple	Watermelon	Sugarcane	Blend
Gompertz	BP	0.1113	0.101	0.091	0.1212	0.1605	0.204
	k	0.01	0.009	0.00893	0.01374	0.0126	0.0126
	LP	14.25	13.89	12.99	13.08	14.321	13.332

	R ²	0.971285	0.961271	0.967459	0.989588	0.926207	0.702788
	Adj. R ²	0.970295	0.959935	0.966337	0.989228	0.923662	0.69252
Logistic	BP	0.352344	0.31335	0.40358	0.37806	0.286968	0.49134
	k	0.01838	0.01619	0.0213	0.019847	0.014713	0.02636
	LP	15.7594	15.8987	15.6041	15.6765	16.00878	15.39618
	R ²	9.16984	9.43078	8.8696	9.01379	9.62676	8.43765
	Adj. R ²	9.52052	9.79046	9.20993	9.35909	9.9932	8.76309
First-Order	BP	10.4526	9.345	8.9768	7.7209	10.0013	11.3376
	k	0.1567	0.0895	0.1122	0.0876	0.1456	0.1732
	R ²	0.50227	0.427381	0.45718	0.395069	0.477422	0.542286
	Adj. R ²	0.485108	0.407636	0.43846	0.37421	0.459402	0.546502

It is always recommended to characterize feedstock to be used for biogas production, as the absence of most of these elements will result in microbial death at the early stage of the process. Especially the lag phase when microbes are just on the verge of adapting to the environment they find themselves.

3.1.3. | Biogas Yield

Cumulative biogas yield (CBY) from separate digestion of the 5 FW types and their blend with retention time (RT) is shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Experimental Biogas Yield of the FW

Fig. 2 shows that, there is an increase in the CBY with time to a peak value for all lines of the FW experimental data obtained. In hierarchical order, the highest yield is blend,

followed by pineapple, watermelon, banana, orange peels and sugarcane bagasse for the 30 days retention period examined. In all the plots, it is clear that from 0-6 days, no yield of gas was recovered, as it took 6 days for the microorganisms to settle hypothetically (a phase called lag phase, LP). This follows a steady increase in gas yield before almost stabilizing at an optimum value. The period in which there is constant increase in gas yield corresponds to the period when the microorganisms are actively carrying out metabolic activities within the reactor they are kept.

3.1.4. | Model Fitting

The 3 models fitted to experimental values shown in Fig. 2 is as shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Representations of Excel Estimates of CBY of the FW from the Three Models

Similarly, when the experimental result was fitted to modified Gompertz model, Logistic model and First-Order model as shown in Fig. 3, identical pattern is obtained in the corresponding model. However, a longer LP is shown in Fig 3a as against Fig. 3b. Predicted plot of the line for the Logistic model gives same LP compared to the experimental CBY plot in Fig. 2. Also, only the Logistic model ranks the line of the FW in the order described previously from blend to sugarcane bagasse. Modified Gompertz and First-Order model disorderly gives the pattern of yield. Comparing the model plot with the empirical one, it is clear that the First-Order model is the worst-performing model, given that the LP is

missing in the plot. Though normally, absence of LP signifies a quick on set of gas generation which is not in-line with what is seen in Fig. 2. Excel Solver estimates of the 3-model parameter with the coefficient of determination (R^2) and adjusted R^2 for all six waste samples is shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Model Predicted Constant and Statistical Parameters for Each Fruit Waste

Based on R^2 and adjusted R^2 obtained utilizing the modified Gompertz model, it could be said that the model is the most suitable model for the type of data obtained empirically. The two statistical parameters obtained in Logistic and First-Order model are either negative or below 50% degree of fit, making them the worst performing model for the FW biogas yield result.

4.0. | Conclusion

Biogas was successfully produced using the FW taken in the order of CBY = 0.30022 kg blended waste, 0.23841 kg pineapple waste, 0.22075 kg watermelon waste, 0.20309 kg banana waste, 0.1766 kg orange waste and 0.15894 kg sugarcane bagasse. There is no any noticeable inhibitor influencing the gas production looking at a smooth trend portrayed by the gas production plot for all FW. The parameters, BP, k and LP are different in all models used. However, a blend of fruit waste, according to the modified Gompertz estimate has the highest BP. Overall, the best model is modified Gompertz.

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Project Management	
Means	

Ehime II

Writing-original draft	
Writing-revision and editing	
Discussion of Result	X
Review and approval of the final version	

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